

Flux-Like Probability $\exp(ipx)$ Guaranteeing One Dimensional Photon Reflection-Refraction Probability Conservation

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Consider the problem of a photon moving in the x direction in a medium with index of refraction n_1 and striking an interface along the y axis at $x=0$ with $n_2=n_1$ for $x>0$. It is evident that $1 = \text{Probability}(\text{reflect}) + \text{Probability}(\text{refract})$, but this equation does not yield the relative probability ratio. One might try to apply maximization of Shannon's entropy subject to the constraint $\sum_i P(i) = 1$ ((1)). This, however, like for a coin, yields probabilities of .5 which do not match experiment. What is wrong? First, it seems like there are more constraints in the problem which have been overlooked in the constraint ((1)). For instance, $E=pc$ and E is constant for all x . There is a discontinuity in p (momentum) and speed at $x=0$. The speed of light in a medium with index of refraction is c/n_i where c is the speed in a vacuum. Thus we suggest a kind of motion related equilibrium throughout the medium. This same idea applies to p , momentum. How does one characterize such an equilibrium. In (1), we suggested a probability $P(x)$ obtained by maximizing Shannon's entropy subject to the periodic constraint $\int p \cdot x \cdot P(x)$ with p being the Lagrange multiplier. Here we point out that this maximization of entropy is equivalent to the statement that $P(p,x)P(-p,x) = 1$. Thus a very different kind of equilibrium i.e. maximization of Shannon's entropy exists. One does not maximize a Shannon's entropy based on allowable state results as in the toss of a coin or die, or a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas. The equation $P(\text{reflect})+P(\text{refract})=1$, however, is based on state probabilities and we ask: Why is it guaranteed to exist if one uses an equilibrium based on $\exp(ipx)$ flux-like probabilities?

Given the constraint that E is the same for all x , a particle reflecting at $x=0$ back into $x<0$ has no choice but to have a momentum of $-p$. This has important consequences on the link between the $\exp(ipx)$ flux-like probability and the state probabilities $P(\text{reflect})$, $P(\text{refract})$. In fact, we argue that it guarantees that a probability calculation using $\exp(ipx)$ yields $P(\text{reflect})+P(\text{refract}) = 1$. In (2), for example, such a relationship is shown to exist, but it is not explained why it must exist.

Flux-Like Probability

Probability is often used to describe states. For example, for a coin there are two states, heads and tails and hence two corresponding probabilities. For a photon moving in the x direction and reflecting/refracting at x (from a plane along y with an n_1-n_2 interface) there are reflected and refracted states. These are mutually exclusive and each has their own probability, although it seems there is no way to find the relative probability.

We have suggested that a photon moving through a medium with a certain index of refraction is in equilibrium with this medium. This is flux-like probability because it exists for all x and is an explicit function of x . It is a dynamic probability. Flux for a particle with constant p is constant in x , but loses information about p and its interaction with the medium. In (1) we suggested that the flux-like probability is linked to the maximization of Shannon's entropy subject to a periodic constraint involving x average and the Lagrange multiplier p . We thus introduce two probabilities for a photon moving along x and reflecting/refracting at $x=0$. There is the dynamic flux-like probability and the state probabilities $P(\text{reflect})$, $P(\text{refract})$. The flux-like probability is due to an

equilibrium between the momentum and the medium and so seems not be linked in a simple manner to the state probabilities. We wish to show, however, that the flux-like probability guarantees the state probability equation:

$$1 = P(\text{reflect}) + P(\text{refract}) \quad ((2))$$

Maximization of Shannon's entropy $- \sum P(x) \ln(P(x))$ subject to the periodic constraint $i p x P(x)$, where p is the Lagrange multiplier, yields $\exp(ipx)$. At first this calculation may seem somewhat superficial, but we argue it is equivalent to the approach used to find the Maxwell-Boltzmann factor for reaction balance. In that case,

$e_1 + e_2$ is associated with $P(e_1)pPe_2$, the probability for an e_1 to collide with an e_2 , so that $\ln(P(e_1))$ is equated to $-ei/T$.

Here, if one uses $p-p$ and $P(p,x)P(-p,x)$, then

$$\ln(P(p,x)) = \text{constant} * p \quad ((3)).$$

This leads to $\exp(ipx)$ if $P(p,x)=P(px)$ and a periodic constant is used. One may note the link of $\exp(i \theta)$ to two periodic functions, $\cos(\theta)$ and $\sin(\theta)$. What does $P(px)P(-px)$ mean? It seems to imply there is flux in both directions and so one cannot distinguish any x probability features associated with motion in one direction. (This is not the same as $\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx)$ for a particle in a box.) $((3))$ is equivalent to Shannon's maximization of entropy subject to a periodic constraint and we argue that it gives a somewhat more physical picture of $\exp(ipx)$. Thus a momentum is associated with a flux-like probability which describes its equilibrium with a medium (even a vacuum). How is this then linked to specific state probability results such as reflection and refraction?

$\exp(ipx)$ Guaranteeing $P(\text{reflect})+P(\text{refract})=1$

Consider a discontinuity along the y -axis for two media with indices of refraction n_1 and n_2 . There is a discontinuity in the speed of light, c/n_1 and c/n_2 , but E , energy, is constant for all x . Given that $E=pc$, this yields different p values in each medium. As a result, a particle in the region $x < 0$ can only have p or $-p$ for its momentum (if E is constant). This, we argue, is critical to establishing $((2))$ i.e. the usual state based probability conservation equation.

We first reiterate that a particle with momentum p creates an equilibrium with the medium characterized by the dynamic flux-like probability $\exp(ipx)$. Given the discontinuities in p at $x=0$, we argue one should create an $\exp(ipx)$ based continuity equation at $x=0$ as well as making its derivative continuous (equivalent to a kind of momentum times flux probability balance) i.e.

$$A \exp(ipx) + B \exp(-ipx) = C \exp(ip_2x) \text{ at } x=0 \quad \text{where } p \text{ is the momentum in } n_1=1 \quad ((4a))$$

$$\text{And } A p \exp(ipx) - B p \exp(-ipx) = p_2 C \exp(ip_2x) \quad ((4b))$$

Given that the form $\exp(ipx)$ follows from $P(px)P(-px)=1$, we consider multiplying ((4a)) by its complex conjugate. This yields:

$$AA + BB + AB^2 \cos(2px) = CC \quad ((5)) \quad \text{At } x=0 \text{ there exist mixed terms i.e. } 2AB.$$

Thus ((5),) which seems to be linked to flux in space, is not mutually exclusive for reflected and refracted photons, i.e. there exists the mixing term $2AB\cos(2px)$ which oscillates in space.

How does one obtain mutual exclusivity which is required in ((2)). We argue that the existence of p and $-p$ in $x<0$ which follows from constant E and c_1 being a constant for $x<0$ is the key. The momentum conservation type equation is guaranteed to be the second part of a difference of squares term i.e. one has $A+B=C$ and $pA - pB = C$ at $x=0$. This, in turn, guarantees the elimination of the cross-term involving the product AB leaving only AA, BB and CC terms which describe the mutual exclusivity required for state probability conservation. This elimination, however, occurs only at $x=0$. For instance, taking the complex conjugate of ((4a)) and multiplying by ((4b)) yields:

$$W^*(x) (-id/dx) W(x) = AA + BB + 2ABi \sin(2px) \quad \text{for } x>0 \quad ((6))$$

Thus, we argue that the equilibrium flux-like probability, together with function and first derivative continuity at $x=0$ and the E constant constraint not only solves the one-dimensional reflection-refraction problem (i.e. yields B and C in terms of A), but guarantees the state based probability equation ((2)). ((2)) is an evident equation to write, but does not solve the problem. In (2) it is noted that ((4a)) and ((4b)) combine to yield ((2)), but no proof is given as to why this must be the case.

One may note that the ((2)) is equivalent to: $AAp = BBp + CCp^2$, or using $E=pc$, $AA/c = BB/c + CC/c^2$. Thus, AA, BB, CC are fluxes. Photon number and energy are conserved as quantities by ((2)), but momentum is not. Rather flux time momentum (i.e. pressure) seems to be balanced at the discontinuity point $x=0$. $\exp(ipx)$, however, is linked to momentum conservation for a particle with a constant p . At $x=0$, however, one must add $A\exp(ipx)$ and the reflected $B\exp(ipx)$ on the LHS side and link them to $C\exp(ip2x)$ on the RHS.

Conclusion

For a photon moving in the x direction and striking an n_1-n_2 (index of refraction) interface along y at $x=0$, it seems evident that $P(\text{reflect})+P(\text{refract})=1$, but this does not yield the relative probabilities. Maximizing Shannon's entropy subject to $\sum_i P(i) = 1$, like for a coin, yields .5 which does not match experiment. We argue that such an approach ignores the constraints in the system i.e. $E=pc$ and E constant for all x . These two have important consequences because they force a reflected photon to have momentum $-p$. This, we argue, is critical in ensuring mutual exclusivity of $P(\text{reflect})$ and $P(\text{refract})$ at $x=0$.

We argue that the equilibrium in the problem is between p (momentum) and the medium. This, we suggest, leads to an x -dependent flux-like probability which exists everywhere in the medium. It may be calculated by maximizing Shannon's entropy $-P(x) \ln(P(x))$ subject to a periodic constraint $i p x P(x)$ or from $P(px)P(-px)=1$. The latter shows that the x dependence of

$\exp(ipx)$ is used to demonstrate p flux in one direction. We suggest that for the reflection-refraction problem one use a continuous $\exp(ipx)$ like equation and a continuous first derivative i.e. $W(x) = A\exp(ipx) + B\exp(-ipx) = C\exp(ip2x)$ and $A\exp(ipx) - B\exp(-ipx) = C\exp(ip2x)$ at $x=0$. These two equations may be used to solve for B,C in terms of A. Why do they also guarantee the state based probability conservation: $P(\text{reflect}) + P(\text{refract})=1$? We argue that this follows from the reflected photon having $-p$ due to $E=pc$ and $E=\text{constant}$ for all x . We note that $P(px)P(-px) = 1$ for a free particle, but not for $W^*(x)W(x)$. Even at $x=0$ there is a $2AB$ term which breaks the mutual exclusivity of reflection/refraction. How does one obtain mutual exclusivity? $W^*(x) (-id/dx) W(x)$ guarantees mutual exclusivity because the reflected ray has momentum $-p$. This leads to a difference of squares (due to the reflected $-p$) which eliminates an AB term at $x=0$, although it exists for $x<0$. As a result, the continuity (and first derivative) continuity of a probability based on $\exp(ipx)$ (an equilibrium with the medium) result for each momentum in the problem (instead of maximizing Shannon's entropy for the various state results) not only solves the problem, but guarantees an equation with no AB mixing at $x=0$ which represents the mutual exclusivity of $1 = P(\text{reflect}) + P(\text{refract})$ which also must hold.

References

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2. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Reflection_phase_change